

**LESSON PLANNING-DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONS (DI) AS MEANS OF
POWERFUL TOOL FOR LEARNER MOTIVATION DUE TO MULTIPLE
INTELLIGENCE DIFFERENCES**

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Abstract:

In this article highlights of the problem of individualization of education of students and differentiating classroom instructions for the needs of the students according to multiple intelligence measurement.

Key words: individualization, differentiating classroom, multiple intelligence, teacher – student, pedagogic skill

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XXI century modern approaches to enhancing learning effectiveness focus on fostering positive motivation for students to engage in studying and developing the ability to acquire and apply knowledge throughout their lives and activities. To fully unlock the developmental potential of these aspects in the educational activities of students with mental retardation, a tailored and differentiated approach is essential. The Multiple Intelligences theory challenges the notion of a singular, general intelligence by proposing eight distinct types of intelligence. Each type is valuable, and success in different areas may be influenced by specific intelligences. For instance, a person strong in musical intelligence but weak in visual-spatial intelligence may excel in music class but face challenges in art class. The issue of individualizing education for students and adolescents has been a concern since ancient times, particularly with the advent of mass education. In the past, when education primarily occurred at home, teachers relied on individual pedagogical experience, intuition, and understanding of a child's motives, inclinations, and abilities. However, as education shifted to larger classes, individualized teaching methods based on a teacher's experience became impractical. The drawbacks of frontal education for large student groups were soon recognized and prompted research into alternative methods. A logical and effective solution to address the negative impacts of frontal learning was to group students based on factors significantly affecting learning effectiveness.

The State Standard is based on a system-activity approach, conceptually based on ensuring that students' educational activities correspond to their age and individual characteristics. The system-activity approach involves taking into account the individual age, psychological and physiological characteristics of students, the role and significance of activities and forms of communication to determine the goals of education and upbringing and ways to achieve them. The essence of the principle of an individual approach is to take into account the individual characteristics of students in the educational process in order to actively manage the development of their mental and physical capabilities.

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Usually the class consists of students with different development and degree of preparedness, different academic performance and different attitude to learning, different interests and health status. Teachers focus on strong students, selecting teaching methods and techniques, pushing weak students to the second and third plan. If the individual characteristics characteristic of some mentally retarded student will be observed in others, then such features are called typical, i.e. inherent in a certain group of students. To implement a differentiated approach, it is necessary, first of all, to differentiate students into groups. In education system practice, in a number of cases, a simple differentiation of students into strong, average and underachieving is used. It helps the teacher to implement a differentiated approach to some extent. But this differentiation does not take into account the reasons for the difficulties of student in learning and does not make it possible to help students cope with difficulties and advance in the assimilation of educational material. However, the reasons for their lag are different: one is lagging behind due to local motor disorders, having a relatively preserved intelligence, manifested in the ability to analyze the features of the product, plan work and adequately evaluate it, the other is due to a low level of intellectual development and the associated pathological slowness of movements. Due to various reasons for lagging behind, these students cannot be assigned to the same group and the measures of a differentiated approach to them are significantly different. Further study of the problem of pedagogical differentiation of students and the development of measures of a differentiated approach in teaching basic academic subjects will more specifically identify the specific features of this didactic principle of the auxiliary education system. An individual approach is of great importance in assessing academic performance, since mentally retarded education system student, due to the heterogeneity of the defect, have different educational opportunities. The assessment of their academic performance cannot be based on general assessment norms, it must take into account the degree of student advancement, stimulate the process of his learning and perform an educational function. The differentiated approach is based on different opportunities for students to master the program material. 4 groups of students are identified, depending on the possibilities of their assimilation of educational material and their typological features are determined. The first group consists of students who most successfully master the program material in the process of frontal training. All tasks are usually performed by them independently. They do not experience great difficulties when performing a modified task, mostly correctly use the existing experience when doing a new job. The ability to explain their actions in words testifies to the conscious assimilation of program material by these students. Group II students are also quite successful in the classroom. In the course of training, these student experience somewhat greater difficulties than the students of group I. They mostly understand the teacher's frontal explanation, memorize the studied material well, but they are not able to draw elementary conclusions and generalizations without help. They are distinguished by less independence in performing all types of work, they need the help of a teacher, both activating and organizing. Transferring knowledge to new conditions does not make it difficult for them in the main. Group III includes students who have difficulty assimilating program material, needing various types of help (verbal-logical, visual and subject-practical). The success of learning, first of all, depends on the student's understanding of what is being communicated to them. It is difficult for them to understand the material during

frontal classes, they need additional explanation. They are distinguished by low independence. The rate of assimilation of the material in these students is significantly lower than in student assigned to group II. Despite the difficulties of mastering the material, students generally do not lose the acquired knowledge and skills, they can apply them when performing a similar task, but each slightly modified task is perceived by them as new. Group IV includes students who master the educational material of the auxiliary education system at the lowest level. At the same time, only frontal training is clearly not enough for them. They need to perform a large number of exercises, the introduction of additional training techniques, constant monitoring and prompts during the execution of work. To draw conclusions with some degree of independence, it is not possible for them to use past experience. Students need a clear repeated explanation from the teacher when performing any task. The teacher's help in the form of a direct hint is used correctly by some students, while others make mistakes in these conditions. These students do not see mistakes in their work, they need a specific indication of them and an explanation for correction. Each subsequent task is perceived by them as a new one. Knowledge is acquired purely mechanically, quickly forgotten. Types of differentiation in education: External differentiation (organization of special education system s, opening classes with advanced training or correctional, electives, elective courses, etc.). Internal differentiation, when within the framework of a regular class for groups of students who have similar (significant for the educational process) individual characteristics, the most rational nature of work in the classroom, elective courses, elective courses are determined (granting students the right to choose a number of subjects to study in addition to compulsory academic disciplines). Differentiation of the content of educational knowledge can be carried out: - by the level of creativity. (Non-creative performance of tasks is work on a model, work on the reproduction of knowledge. Creative tasks include exercises that differ from the standard ones); -by difficulty level; -by volume (In addition to the main one, an additional task is performed similar to the main one. This is due to the different pace of students' work. Differentiation by volume is combined with other ways, there may be creative or more difficult tasks. Additional tasks may be tasks for ingenuity, tasks of a game nature). I propose to consider the differentiation by the level of complexity on the example of a split picture. I note that in correctional work with student with intellectual disabilities, it is customary to use split pictures, not puzzles. Or you can use different ways of organizing student's educational activities and single tasks, differentiate by: - degree of independence. (All student do the same task, but some do it under the guidance of a teacher, and others independently) - the nature of student assistance. (This job does not involve front-line work under the guidance of a teacher. All students immediately start independent work. But those students who are experiencing difficulties are assisted in the form of: • auxiliary cards, • preparatory exercises, • entries on the board. The helper cards are either the same for all student of the group, or are selected individually. There are many ways to help students prepare for homework: - point out analogies, - explain with examples, - to sort out the difficult sides of the tasks. - explain the content of the work, - give the algorithm, - to inform the methods of completing tasks. Additional research may be needed in order to understand the best possible methods to assess and support a range of intelligence in the classroom. For now, the theory has already taught students, teachers, parents, and administrators to broaden their definition of intelligence

and to include all types in the equation. The best way to layout a classroom to support multiple intelligences is to have places in the room that works for each type of intelligence. For linguistic intelligence, there should be a quiet area for reading, writing, and practicing speeches. For logical-mathematical intelligence, there should be an area where students can conduct scientific experiments. For visual-spatial intelligence, include an open area for object manipulation or art creation. For bodily-kinesthetic intelligences, an open area for body movement could be provided. For musical intelligence, including a separate area for music listening and creating, perhaps with soundproofing or headphones. For naturalistic intelligence, outdoor space or indoor aquarium or terrarium could be provided. For interpersonal intelligence, there should be an area with large tables for group work, while for intrapersonal intelligence there should be areas for individual activities. Thus, differentiated tasks, differentiated assessment, being part of a differentiated approach, create a situation of success for students with intellectual disabilities for further development, which is an incentive in learning and, as a result, a solid assimilation of program material.

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